

DORIVOR ACHCHIQ BODOM URUG'INING SHIFOBAXSHLIGI, DORI TAYYORLASH USULLARI.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049433>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 22-October 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 24- October 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 28- October 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

COVID-19 global pandemiya davrida va hozirgi paytda epidemiyani nazorat qilish uchun ishlatiladigan dori vositalari juda kam.

ABSTRACT

Maqola shuni ko'rsatadiki tirnoqgul o'simligining dorivorlik xususiyatlari va o'simlikdan tayyorlangan turli xil maxsulotlarni ishlatilishi va turli soxalarda qo'llash yo'llari yoritilgan..

Dorivor tirnoqgul (*Calendula officinalis* L). - Vatani Janubiy va Markaziy Yevropa. O'rta Osiyoning barcha respublikalarida manzarali va dorivor o'simlik sifatida ko'p ekiladi. Ushbu dorivor o'simlik astraguldoshlar oilasiga mansub.

Yana bu o'simlik **kalendula** nomi bilan ham ko'pchiligimizga ma'lum. Bu o'simlik qadim zamonlardan beri xalq tabobatida ham keng miqyosda foydalanilib kelinmoqda. Hozirda rasmiy tibbiyotga ham keng qo'llanilmoqda.

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Achchiq bodom (*Amygdalus communis* L. Varietasamara D.C.) urug'larini po'stloqlaridan tozalab sovuq yoki issiq presslash usulida moy olinadi. Achchiq bodom urug'i tarkibida to'yinmagan yog' kislotalaridan olein (66,69 % dan 69,5 % gacha), linolen (18,86 % dan 22,31% gacha) ni tashkil etsa, to'yingan yog' kislotalaridan palmitin (5,71 % gacha) stearin 1.50% ni tashkil qiladi. Umumiy efir moyining 99,90% ni tashkil etadigan 21 xil tarkibiy qismlar aniqlangan, ulardan benzaldegid (62,52 %), benzoin kislotasi (14,80%) va geksadekan (3,97 %) eng ko'p tarqalgan komponentlardir. Achchiq bodom mag'zi uning tarkibida amigdalın glikozidi borligi uchun zaharli hisoblanadi. Amigdalın suv tasirida parchalanganda hayot uchun zaharli bo'lgan benzaldegid va sianid kislotasi hosil bo'ladi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

COVID-19 global pandemiya davrida va hozirgi paytda epidemiyani nazorat qilish uchun ishlatiladigan dori vositalari juda kam. Ammo ko'plab klinik amaliyotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, xitoyning an'anaviy tibbiyot epidemiyani davolashda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Ular orasida efedra-achchiq bodom anti-COVID-19 retseptlarida keng tarqalgan qo'shma dori hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot tarmoq farmakologiyasi asosida COVID-19 efedra-achchiq bodomga qarshi vositalarining asosiy tarkibiy qismlari va mexanizmlarini o'rganishga

qaratilgan . Achchiq bodom moyini tashqaridan surish bilan ultrabinafsha nurlanishidan himoya qilish, yog' bezlarini normal holatiga olib kelish va teri teshiklarining kengayishini oldini olish tufayli terining qarishi jarayoni sezilarli darajada sekinlashadi. Achchiq bodom uzoq davom etadigan yo'tal uchun samarali vosita bo'lib, ichki a'zolari tozalaydi, nafas qisilishi, plevrit va qonda qusishni to'xtatadi. Ibn Sino tinnitus va quloq og'rig'ini achchiq bodom yoki bodom moyi pyuresi bilan davolashni tavsiya qilgan, shuningdek, uni sochlarni yuvish va kepakdan xalos bo'lish uchun uni musallas bilan aralashtirib ishlatishni taklif qilgan. Achchiq bodom kukuni terini sepkillar, xollar va qarishdan himoya qiladi. Achchiq bodom moyining tarkibi xilma-xilligi uning yetishtirilgan joyiga bog'liq.

Achchiq bodom bo'tqasi kosmetikada tavsiya etiladi. O'zining foydali taraflari bilan achchiq bodom ko'pdan beri xalq tabobatida o'z o'rniga ega. Uning ichishga buyuriladigan qaynatmasi ko'zga davo. Achchiq bodom yuzdagi sepkillarni ketkazadi.

XULOSA

Bodom mag'zini chuqur qayta ishlash texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish bu mahsulot asosida biofaol moddalar, dori preparatlari, oqsillar va boshqa mahsulotlar olish imkoniyatini beradi. Achchiq bodomning suvli, etanol ishtirokidagi, hatto maydalangan achchiq bodom mag'zining kukunlari ularning tarkibida amigdalın diglyukozidi borligi uchun muhim mahsulot hisoblanishini e'tiborga olish kerak. Hozirgi kunda achchiq bodom moyi teriga ta'sir qiluvchi va teri hamda sochlarni parvarishida keng qo'llanilmoqda. Lekin ana shu zaharli modda o'zini namoyon etadigan preparatlar olish zarur

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